

DESIGN, ANALYSIS AND FABRICATION OF AN ADVANCED COMPOSITE TUBULAR T-JOINT

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ABSTRACT

The Finite Element Method (FEM) is used to design and analyze a tubular T-joint made entirely of graphite/epoxy. The design incorporates a flared transition surface at the intersection of the brace and chord tube to maximize load flow and maintain a direct load path. Details of FEM model formulation and application in terms of geometric and material compatibilities and boundary conditions are discussed. Predictions are compared with results of instrumented T-joints tested to failure. Results indicate that FEM predicts the elastic behaviour and load capacity with reasonable accuracy. To accommodate the geometric complexity, a new manufacturing technique is developed and verified through a component test program.

Keywords: Truss Joint, Tubular Joint, Graphite/Epoxy, Composites, Lightweight Structures, Space Structures, Finite Element Method

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced composites such as graphite/epoxy in space structures has been driven by the need for dimensional stability, increased specific stiffness and low mass. Many structures use these material systems to produce spacecraft structures which are improved over structures utilizing more conventional materials. Although the Hubble Large Space Telescope uses a metering truss composed entirely of graphite/epoxy^[1], similar skeletal structures typically use metal end fittings to connect structural elements at nodal intersections. The composite tubular elements can be tailored to possess zero Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE). The metal fittings will contribute significantly to the expansion and contraction of a member even if its length is only a few percent of the total member length. This undesirable distortion can be compensated for by the composite tube having a negative CTE but the adhesive which joins the tube and fitting together will be exposed to severe loading due to CTE mis-match^[2]. For structures used for robotic applications and having a high nodal density, the advantage gained in using lightweight composite tubes can be negated easily by the use of massive fittings at cluster joints^[3]. Hence, the development of a mass-efficient joint made entirely of advanced composite materials is required to provide a direct load path between members, to reduce stress

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concentrations and material discontinuities, and be designed such that the skeletal system lines of a space frame structure remain unaffected by thermal excursions.

This effort is part of a program to define and develop efficient joints and joining techniques to promote the use of advanced composites in spacecraft and satellite structures. Great potential exists in developing such techniques to define highly optimized structural forms. The focus of this paper is to assess the benefit of incorporating a flared transition between two intersecting tubes composed of graphite/epoxy, in an effort to develop a joint which rivals welding in metals, in mass, stiffness and strength efficiency.

The steps toward this objective include:

- (i) developing finite element models of composite T-joints, focusing on verification of FEM predictions of strains via structural testing,
- (ii) fabricating test articles to support FEM verification while at the same time investigating manufacturing issues such as fiber placement and processing.

2. BACKGROUND

Several investigators have developed successfully composite joints for skeletal structures [5-9], many utilizing braiding or filament winding techniques. The most impressive is a three-dimensional T-joint recently developed by Kobayashi [5]. The *Mathweb* concept^[10] avoids the joining problem by filament winding of open lattice structures, with fibre interleaving at the nodal points. Fiber orientations are necessarily limited, and mass efficient, minimum-gauge tubular structural elements are not easily formed using the process.

In a 1956 German patent, Petri^[4] developed a *tent connection* for joining welded metallic tubular members together. An angle-shaped member placed on top of a chord tube received brace tubes and prevented undesirable local buckling by introducing the load near the chord tube neutral axis of bending. Additionally, it provided ample area for load flow through the connection. This design philosophy was extended to composite material joints in Reference [3]. A novel joint was developed which employed a sculptured transition surface, placing fibers into a position where they could contribute efficiently to load transfer. All of the above studies have focused primarily on the manufacturing methodology as opposed to the creation of validated, three-dimensional analytical models.

3. DESIGN

The design proposed in this paper improves upon the joint in [3] by creating a hollow tubular connection, and by moving the joint outside of the member centreline intersection. The key to the design is the flared transition surface. Hence, the joining concept proposes that:

- (i) an integral fitting be manufactured in tubular form, of minimum gage, incorporating a flared transition shape,
- (ii) the fitting to member joint be kept outside the skeletal system line intersection,
- (iii) fiber placement in the fitting be tailored to reduce substantially or eliminate totally axial and/or circumferential distortion of the legs of the fitting.

The T-joint model proposed for study is shown in Figure 1. Its general dimensions were chosen to be representative of typical space structure size (i.e. about 50 mm chord tube diameter, 25 mm brace tube diameter). Fortafil 3(C) graphite/epoxy was chosen as the material system and a hand

lay-up technique, described in a later section, was used to fabricate test articles. This technique required that an overlap region exist (referred to as a *skirt* region) between the brace tube laminate and the chord tube laminate, in the transition region (i.e. similar to a *lap* joint). Initial FEM modeling revealed that an interwoven laminate sequence was more integral than a simple lap-type joint. To investigate the effect of flare size, two joints were defined. An *axisymmetric* flared joint, incorporating a tapered collar in fabrication, and a generously *flared* joint were defined based initial analysis and fabrication studies. For this study the laminate type was restricted to a quasi-isotropic laminate, and the T-joint tested in tension only.

4. ANALYSIS

4.1 FEM Program Validation

After an extensive survey of various FEM programs, Engineering Mechanics Research Corporation's NISA program was chosen for this study. NISA's composite element library offers 4 and 8-noded quadrilateral plate elements based on general laminate plate theory (GLPT) as opposed to classical laminate plate theory (CLPT), which is more desirable for laminates having large extensional to transverse shear modulus ratios. NISA also offers 3D layered composite element for analyzing thick laminates, where through-the-thickness stresses are critical.

The program was validated on an aluminum T-joint tested in [3]. Due to geometric and loading symmetry, only one-half of the joint was analyzed. A model was developed consisting of 8-noded isoparametric plate/shell elements with a total of 567 nodes and 3,402 degrees of freedom. This element includes the effect of transverse shear, which plays an important role in our analysis, since the span to depth ratio of the chord between the support points is less than 10. The chord tube ends were modeled as tested (i.e. reinforced to prevent undesirable local deformation). The deflection calculated based on the FEM analysis was found to compare favorably with the experimentally measured deflection. An elasto-plastic analysis compared very well with the experimentally observed load-deformation curve.

4.2 Composite T-Joint Modeling

Figure 2 shows the final refined mesh used for the analysis. A preliminary model contained 640 elements, 686 nodes and 3933 active degrees of freedom. The mesh in Figure 2 contains 1744 4-noded laminate plate elements, 1815 nodes with 10,647 active degrees of freedom. Convergence to experimentally measured values of strain was observed in moving to a more refined mesh. The results of the analysis are presented in Figures 4 and 5 for an intermediate load of 2400N. Strains in the surface layer for both longitudinal (i.e. along the brace tube, skirt and chord tube axes) and transverse directions are presented. The skirt region, defined as the region of overlap between brace tube plies and chord tube plies, consists of an interwoven laminate with a total of 16 plies. The model constructed reflects accurately this lay up sequence (refer to Figure 1). Note that each plate element in the skirt region required proper connectivity reference so that the correct fibre orientation on the complex surface could be accounted for. The material properties used in this model are very similar to an AS-3501 material system. The published values were verified by an in-house material testing program on test coupons.

5. FABRICATION

It was recognized from the outset that Kobayashi's braiding technique could be used to create a quasi-isotropic graphite/epoxy connection. However, the two major objectives of this effort

were to fabricate test articles to verify the FEM model, and to address the fiber placement issues for future low CTE investigations.

A hand layup technique was developed for the axisymmetric T-joint and is presented schematically in Figure 3. Plies of unidirectional prepreg tape were cut into pre-determined shapes and wrapped alternately onto a waxed metal T-shaped mandrel. An epoxy collar is placed on the mandrel to provide a flared surface. After the ply layup is complete, the joint is vacuum debulked and bagged. A thermocouple is placed on the surface of the joint as it is used to monitor laminate temperature during the cure cycle. The bagged joint is then placed on a vacuum table in a fine sand, and oven cured. The sand ensures that the joint is properly consolidated during processing. The mandrel is easily disassembled after cure.

6. TESTING

T-joints were prepared for testing by bonding steel end plugs in the chord tube near the ends to prevent local failure, and in the brace tube end to provide a point of load introduction. The joints were tested in a tensile test fixture in an Instron Universal Testing Machine as shown in Figure 6. Strain gauges were mounted at selected locations to monitor the level of load into the joint region. The tests were carried out at room temperature, at a crosshead speed of 2.5 mm/minute.

A typical load versus strain plot is presented in Figure 7. The failure of the axisymmetric T-joint initiates at location 'A' (see Figure 1), followed by compressive failure of the chord tube in the region of the joint *can* (i.e. the chord tube in the region of the connection). The load-strain behaviour is linear to failure.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 1 and 2 compare the results of the FEM modeling and the experimentally measured strains. The results compare favorably with discrepancies ranging from 2% to about 40%. The more disparate results are from gauges located in regions of high strain gradient, or at locations where local surface defects dominated the strain behavior. The strains observed indicate that the chord tube deforms to an oval shape, with the major axis of the ellipse in the direction of the applied load. The results indicate that the bottom of the chord tube is in compression, while the circumferential surface strain is tensile at the bottom of the chord. Interestingly, the surface strain state here excludes shear.

The failure load is well predicted by the Hill-Mises failure criterion and not as well predicted by Tsai-Wu. Hill-Mises predicts failure at 4,080 N and Tsai-Wu predicts failure at 8,400 N, compared with an average failure of 4,650 N for the 3 joints tested. Both failure criteria predict failure location accurately.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above analysis, testing and observations we conclude that the FEM predicts with reasonable accuracy the elastic behavior and load capacity of T-joints composed of aluminum or quasi-isotropic graphite/epoxy.

Acknowledgements

The authors are very grateful to Dr. D.G. Zimcik of the Canadian Space Agency for his technical guidance and editorial contributions.

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Table 1: Comparison of FEM Strain Predictions with Experimentally Measured Values (μs) for T-Joint No. 3 and 4 at a Load of 2400N.

Gauge No.	FEM Strain	Joint No. 3 (Failure at 3,800 N)			Joint No. 4 (Failure at 5400 N)		
		Gauge Strain	Average Strain	Discrepancy %	Gauge Strain	Average Strain	Discrepancy %
1	714	586	619	13	969	723	1
2		653			478		
3		896			1092		
10	1002		896	11	1026	1149	17
4		800			884		
5		-1367			-1465		
6	869	-1175	800	8	-1252	884	12
7		174*			-36		
9		-*			120		
8	1998	-*			1884	1884	14

*- Strain gauge rosette improperly bonded

Table 2: Comparison of FEM Strain Predictions with Experimentally Measured Values (μs) for T-Joint No. 5 at a Load of 2400N.

Gauge No.	FEM Strain	Gauge Strain	Discrepancy %
1	-1035	-1160	12
2	2254	2220	2
3	731	-	-
4	2254	2254	2
5	731	-	-
6	1120	1580	41
7	1120	1560	41
8	-2756	-2380	14
9	36	-315	-
10	2305	1940	16

Figure 1: Composite T-joint with axisymmetric flare.

Figure 2: FEM mesh for the axisymmetric flared T-joint.

Figure 3: Typical lamina layup sequence.

Figure 4: Longitudinal surface strain distribution.

Figure 5: Lateral surface strain distribution.

Figure 6: Composite T-joint test setup.

Figure 7: Load-strain behaviour of T-joint No. 5.